

Extended data for F1000 publication "Advancing FAIR Biodiversity Data: Bioschemas Implementation in NFDI4Biodiversity"

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Description

Bioschemas profiles for data types establish comprehensive guidelines that categorize properties into three distinct levels of implementation requirements: Compulsory elements that must contain information, recommended properties that should ideally be included, and optional attributes that may be added based on specific use cases or data availability.

Table 1 presents all mandatory Bioschemas elements of its Dataset type alongside their assigned values within the current mapping version or their equivalent ABCD 2.06 counterparts. These ABCD 2.06 elements used within NFDI4Biodiversity are represented using XPath notation. Notably, the comprehensive mapping demonstrates that all mandatory Bioschemas elements can be successfully addressed through direct mappings from the ABCD 2.06 standard.

The second table shows recommended properties that should ideally contain information about a Dataset but are not strictly required, particularly in situations where such information may be unavailable or inappropriate. The mapping analysis reveals that the vast majority of recommended Bioschemas elements can be accommodated, with only three specific elements (`alternateName`, `includedInDataCatalog`, and `isBasedOn`) remaining uncovered by the current mapping approach.

The final table identifies ABCD elements that cannot be adequately mapped to Bioschemas properties, detailing their sub-elements such as Text or URI in the second column. The accompanying notes column provides detailed explanations regarding the necessity and relevance of these mappings within the context of dataset search use cases. It was found that only two elements have a potential benefit that might be considered relevant for dataset search applications, though this benefit remains limited and somewhat ambiguous.

Mapping information tables

Table 1: Mandatory Bioschemas Dataset Elements with ABCD property equivalents

Bioschemas Dataset Element	Value
@context	https://schema.org/
@type	Dataset
@id	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/DatasetGUID
dct:conformsTo	{ "@id": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/Dataset/1.0-RELEASE", "@type": "CreativeWork" }
description	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Description/Representation/Details
identifier	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/DatasetGUID
keywords	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Scope/GeocologicalTerms/GeocologicalTerm ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Stratigraphy/ChronostratigraphicTerms/ChronostratigraphicTerm/Term ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Stratigraphy/LithostratigraphicTerms/LithostratigraphicTerm/Term ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/KindOfUnit ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Description/Representation/Coverage ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Scope/TaxonomicTerms/TaxonomicTerm ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Biotope/Name ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Project/ProjectTitle
license	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/IPRStatements/Licenses/License
name	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Description/Representation/Title
url	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Description/Representation/URI

Table 2: Recommended Bioschemas Dataset Elements with ABCD property equivalents

Bioschemas Dataset Element	Value
alternateName	<i>Not applicable</i>
citation	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/SourceReference ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/UnitReferences/UnitReference
creator	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/RevisionData/Creators
datePublished	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/RevisionData/DateModified ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/Version/DateIssued
distribution	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/DirectAccessURI
includedInDataCatalog	<i>Not applicable</i>
isBasedOn	<i>Not applicable</i>
measurementTechnique	(ABCD:/MeasurementOrFact/MeasurementOrFactAtomised/Method)
publisher	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/TechnicalContacts/TechnicalContact
variableMeasured	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Altitude ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Depth
version	ABCD:/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/RevisionData/Version/

Table 3: ABCD Dataset Elements Lacking Bioschemas Counterparts

ABCD 2.06 Element	Sub-Elements	Notes
/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/IPRStatements/Copyrights/Copyright/	Text Details URI	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/IPRStatements/Disclaimers/Disclaimer	Text Details URI	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/IPRStatements/IPRDeclarations/IPRDeclaration	Text Details URI	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Metadata/IPRStatements/Acknowledgements/Acknowledgement	Text Details URI	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/LastEditor	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/DateLastEdited	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/AuthorTeam	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/AuthorTeamParenthesis	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/GenusOrMonomial	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/FirstEpithet	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases

/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/InfraspecificEpithet	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Result/TaxonIdentified/ScientificName/NameAtomised/Botanical/Rank	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Identifiers/Identifier	-	Possibly relevant for search
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Identifications/Identification/Date	-	Possibly relevant for search
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/DateTime/DateText	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases
/DataSets/DataSet/Units/Unit/Gathering/Notes	-	Probably not relevant for Dataset search but for other use cases